

Study of Vocational Guidance Need in Relation to Creativity and Gender of Higher Secondary School Students of Indore District

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Abstract

The objective of the study was-(1) To study the influence of Creativity, Gender and their interaction on Vocational Guidance Needs of the students. The hypothesis of the study was- (1) There is no significant influence of Creativity, Gender and their interaction on Vocational Guidance Needs of the students. The study was Survey in nature. Total 500 students from six higher secondary schools of Indore city were selected randomly in the study. Creativity of students were assessed by 'Baquer Mehdi test of Creative Thinking' developed by Baquer Mehdi (1973). The Vocational Guidance needs of students were assessed by the Scale. Vocational Guidance Needs Scale (VGNS) was developed and standardized by the researcher. The reliability coefficient of VGNS was 0.87. The Content validity of VGNS was also ensured. The data was analyzed with the help of 2x2 Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). The findings of study were-(1) The students of high and low creative group were found to have vocational guidance need to same extent. (2) The Males and Female group students were found to have vocational guidance need to same extent. (3) The Vocational Guidance Needs of the students was found to independent of interaction between creativity and gender.

Key Words : Vocational Guidance Needs Scale, Creativity & Gender

Introduction

The complex human personality, modern industrial complexity, complexity of educational subjects and complexity of various vocations have made the vocational system so complicated that it has become almost compulsory to seek the advice of expert to understand the nature of vocations, selection of vocations and entry into the vocations. Without counseling the selection of vocation may prove harmful and it has occurred to due to multiplicity of vocations and rapidly change in conditions the vocation must suit the person and the person must suit the vocation.

According Dictionary of Cambridge is ability to produce or use original and unusual ideas. According to Sternberg (1999) Creativity is a complex and diffuse construct, difficult to define consensually.

Review of Related Literature

Vocational Guidance Needs and Creativity aspect related some major researches have been conducted by Kiangte (1988), Badola (1991), Ghosh (1991), Bhargava (1992), Goutam (1992), Bansal (1995), Saxena (1995), Aima (1999), Kwatra (2000), and Kaur(2001)

Sample

The present study was survey in nature. For the purpose of survey the sample was drawn from the randomly selected six schools of Indore district. There were three Government schools namely, Ahilya Aashram Government Higher Secondary School, Government Higher Secondary School Sanyogitaganj & Swami Vivekanand Government Higher Secondary School and three private schools namely, Annie Besent Higher Secondary School, Alpine Higher Secondary Public School & New City Convent Higher Secondary School. For study purpose 500 students from these schools were selected. Out of this 500 students, 250 were female and 250 were male student. Number of male students belonging government school was 125 and male students belonging private school was 125. Number of female students belonging government school was 125 and female students belonging private school was 125.

Tools

Two tools were used for data collection. To assess students' creativity, 'Baquer Mehdi test of Creative Thinking' developed by Baquer Mehdi (1973) was used. This test included four traits viz-fluency, flexibility, originality and elaboration. The validity coefficient ranging from 0.32 to 0.40. The test-retest reliability was 0.98. To assess student's vocational guidance need, 'Vocational Guidance Needs Scale' (VGNS) was developed and standardized by researcher. This was five point scale with 50 items. The reliability coefficient was 0.87. Content validity was ensured.

Statistical Technique

The data was analyzed with the help of 2x2 Analysis of Variance (ANOVA).

Result and Interpretation

The objective of the study was to study the influence of Creativity, Gender and their interaction on Vocational Guidance Needs of the students. There were two categories of Creativity. These were high and low creative. On the basis of Gender the group was divided in two groups that is Male and Female students. The data were analyzed with help of 2 x2 factorial design ANOVA .the results are given in table 1.

Table 1 : Summary of 2x2 Factorial Design ANOVA for Vocational Guidance Needs, Creativity and Gender

Source of Variance	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-value
Creativity (A)	341.638	1	341.638	0.387
Gender (B)	292.645	1	292.645	0.331
A x B	367.503	1	367.503	0.416
Error	438020.606	496	883.106	
Total	12149637.000	500		

It is evident from table 1 that F-value for creativity is 0.387 which is not significant. It indicates that the mean score of vocational guidance need of high and low creative students did not differ significantly. So there was no significant influence of creativity on vocational guidance needs of the students. In this context, the null hypothesis that there is no significant influence of creativity on vocational guidance needs of students is not rejected. It may, therefore be, said that the students of high and low group were found to have vocational guidance need to same extent.

The F-value for Gender is 0.331 which is not significant it also indicates that the mean score of Males and Females students did not significantly. So there was no significant influence of Gender of student on Vocational Guidance Need. In this context, the null hypothesis that there is no significant influence of Gender on Vocational Guidance Needs of students is not rejected. . It may, therefore be, said that the Males and Female group students were found to have vocational guidance need to same extent.

The F-value for interaction between creativity and Gender of the students is 0.416 which is not significant. It shows that there is no significant influence of interaction between creativity and Gender of the students on Vocational Guidance Needs. In this context, the null hypothesis that

there is no significant influence of interaction between Creativity and Gender of students on Vocational Guidance Needs is not rejected. It may, therefore be, said that the Vocational Guidance Needs of the students was found to independent of interaction between Creativity and Gender.

Findings

The findings of study were - (1) The students of high and low creative group were found to have vocational guidance need to same extent. (2) The Males and Female group students were found to have vocational guidance need to same extent. (3) The Vocational Guidance Needs of the students was found to independent of interaction between creativity and gender.

Delimitations

To conduct this study some instructions were followed which were stated as following : (1) The study was limited to only six schools of Indore district. (2) The study was subjected to only 500 students. (3) The study was delimited to the higher secondary school students studying in the schools of Indore district. (4) The present study was restricting to study the variable Vocational Guidance Need and Creativity.

:: References ::

- Aima, N.: A Study of School Climate and its relationship with Creativity, Personality and Academic Achievement of Adolescents, Ph.D. (Edu.), Punjab University, 1999.
- Badola, S.: Locus of Control, Achievement – Motivation Anxiety as Correlates of Creativity, Ph.D.(Edu.), Hemwati Nandan Bahuguna Garhwal Unniversity, 1991.
- Bansal, S.: A Comparative Study of High Creative and Low Creative Students in Relation to Their Adjustment Vocational, Interests and Academic Achievement, Ph.D. (Edu.), Bundelkhand University, 1995.
- Bhargava, S.: Achievement Motivation and Creativity in Relation to Locus of Control Socio-Culturally Deprived and Non-Deprived Adolescents, Ph.D. (Edu.), Agra Univeristy, 1992.
- Buch, M.B. (ed.): Fifth Survey of Research in Education, National Council of Educational Research and Training, New Delhi, 1988- 92.
- Ghosh, M.C.: A Study in Creativity, Motor Ability, Motor Creativity of Adolescents Students, Ph.D. (Edu.), University of Kalyani, 1991.

Kaur, M.: Self-Concept in Relation to Intellectual Variables, Journal of Educational Research and Extension, Vol. 38., No. 1, 2001.

Khiangte, V.: Non-Cognitive Correlates of Creativity among the Secondary School Students, Ph.D. (Edu.), North Eastern Hill University, 1988.

Kwatra, A.: Understanding of Science Process in Relation to Scientific Creativity Intelligence and Problem Solving Ability of Middle School Students of Bhopal Division, Ph.D. (Edu.), Baraktullaha University, 2000.

Myers, G.E.: Principles and Techniques of Vocational Guidance, McGraw Hill Book Company Inc., Tokyo, 1941.

Saxena, R.: Patterns of Vocational Interest in relation with Creativity Components, Intelligence and Gender, Ph.D. (Psy.), Agra University, 1995.

Sternberg, R.J.: Handbook of Creativity, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 1999.

Torrance, E.P.: Guiding Creative Talents, Prentice Hall New Jersey, 1966.